

MS11: T4.4 Summary of updated TRE provider capabilities

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1. Introduction

The EOSC-ENTRUST project aims to develop a network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in Europe. The main outcomes of the project include a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis and a TRE provider forum to facilitate knowledge exchange. ENTRUST has project partners in 15 countries across Europe who act as TRE service providers. Together, the partners work toward improving technical, legal, and operational TRE standards.

In 2024, the ENTRUST project produced an inventory that gathered data from 19 different TREs, hosted by 18 organisations. This inventory and related summary were published within the project as MS10 - Inventory & summary of current TRE Provider capabilities. The data used in this milestone was gathered through a survey made available to ENTRUST project partners.

In 2025, ENTRUST ran the survey again, this time making it open to all TRE service providers. The TRE Provider work package (WP11) circulated the survey with the aim to broaden the inventory scope beyond ENTRUST project partners, as well as gather new information with an updated survey format. The survey received 25 responses from 24 different host organisations.

This document contains a summary of the 2025 survey results, providing an update on TRE provider capabilities. The number of answers per question is always denoted, with 25 presenting the maximum. At points the summary answers have been edited for clarity, and this is noted throughout. The survey contained several questions on access mechanisms and security measures, which WP11 deemed to be potentially sensitive information. This data has been removed from the updated inventory published alongside this summary document, with Appendix 1 offering some of this data in an anonymised format. Appendix 2 further outlines what kind of information was labelled as sensitive and removed. Summaries of any sensitive data can still be found in this document, with identifying factors and links to specific TREs removed.

Please consult the related resources:

- [MS11 Updated TRE Inventory](#)
- [Transcript of survey questions](#)

In this summary, the term 'TRE' is used for the environments analysed, but the survey data itself will show that this is not necessarily how these environments self-label. TRE should therefore be understood as an umbrella term.

Finally, discussions and conclusions on TRE provider capabilities are provided at the end of this summary.

2. TRE Descriptors

Organisation two-letter country code

25 responses

The 25 responses were spread out across 11 countries: Czechia, Germany, Denmark, Finland, United Kingdom, Greece, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Slovenia, and the United States. The higher uptake in Finland and the UK likely reflects the survey dissemination efforts of CSC, DARE UK, and ELIXIR amongst their networks.

Despite the survey being titled the 'TRE survey', many respondents described their environment with an alternative name, with Secure Processing Environment (SPE) as the most common, and TRE as the second most common amongst the respondents. This was a multi-choice question, so respondents were able to select more than one – for instance HPC might be a functionality of TREs/SPEs, leading to overlap between answers. Remote access system and Data Safe Haven were also common descriptors.

What is the GDPR role of the organisation?

25 responses

The largest proportion of respondents act as data processor (12 responses), with 3 acting as data controller. 10 respondents act in both roles.

What TRE service zones are present?

14 responses

The data on TRE service zones is in part incomplete, with only 14 out of 25 respondents answering this question. This may be due to unfamiliar abbreviations in the question, or because there are differences in terminology across service providers. Amongst responses, RAZ (Research Analytics Zone) and DMZ (Data Management Zone) are commonly present, while DQZ (Data Query Zone) is less common.

Is the environment available only for processing sensitive data use cases?

25 responses

The environment use between multi-purpose and sensitive data only is almost even, with 13 responses for multi-purpose and 12 for sensitive data only.

Is the service available only for public benefit purposes?

25 responses

The TREs captured in the survey are evenly split between public benefit and non-public benefit environments, with 12 responses each. One respondent marked the question as non-applicable.

3. Access and Accessibility

3.1 Access mechanisms

Question	Yes	No
Is there a self-service user login?	76%	24%
Is there a two-factor authentication?	84%	16%
Is there a single sign-on?	80%	20%

Table 1. Responses regarding authentication (n = 25).

TRE-specific answers to access mechanism questions have been considered as sensitive data and have thus been removed from the updated inventory. The table above offers an overview of this data. The most common access mechanism was two-factor authentication, followed by single-sign on. At 76%, self-service user login was the least common.

3.2 International Accessibility

This question had the following options, as well as “other”:

- Only national access possible
- Access from other EU countries
- Access from other EEA countries
- Non-EU access possible

Respondents interpreted these geographical scopes differently, with many opting for “other” to clarify the accessibility of their environment. These responses can be found in full in the inventory. For clarity, these responses have been reformatted in the chart above. (e.g. “worldwide” is placed under “non-EU access possible”).

The majority of environments have non-EU access, with the number potentially rising from responses that stated access changes between environments according to permits. 16% of environments only allow national level access.

From what region can the PI be registered?

- Dependant on project/organisation permits
- EEA countries plus European Commission accepted third countries
- Non-EU registration possible
- Only national registration possible
- Registration from other EEA countries

This question had the following options, as well as “other”:

- Only national registration possible
- Registration from other EU countries
- Registration from other EEA countries
- Non-EU registration possible

Respondents interpreted these geographical scopes differently, with many opting for “other” to clarify the accessibility of their environment. These responses can be found in full in the inventory. For clarity, these responses have been reformatted in the chart above (e.g. “globally” is placed under “non-EU registration possible”).

The answers are evenly distributed between national PI registration only and non-EU PI registration. Here, too, the project specifics determine PI registration. The survey did not provide a definition of a PI, and there is likely variation across respondents as to how a PI is conceptualised. To get more defined answers, a definition will be provided and/or asked for in the next iteration of the survey.

From what region can non-PI project members be registered?

24 responses

The question for project member registration did not have “other” as an option. Here 66% cited global registration as possible, with 16% reporting only national registration. The remainder is split between EU and EEA registration.

Is there a premise/private cloud, public cloud, or hybrid?

25 responses

Nearly two thirds of environments have a premise/private cloud, with a public cloud the second most common, and a hybrid cloud receiving three responses.

4. Data Types and Security

4.1 Accepted Data Types

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed data types. These responses can be found in full in the inventory.

Spreadsheet files and source code received the most responses with 72% of respondents reporting these to be accepted in their environments, with plain text files, document files, and images coming in at 68%.

Many also responded with “unrestricted data types”, while also ticking different data types accepted. Three respondents further clarified that all types are accepted (“all”, “currently no restrictions”, “platform does not impose restrictions”). Overall, 19 of the environments captured in the survey do not restrict data types, denoting 76%.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed data types. These responses can be found in full in the inventory.

Many responded with “unrestricted”, while also ticking different data types exported. Overall, 13 of the environments do not restrict data types for export, denoting 54%.

4.2 Auditing and Security

Does the service have an ISO27001 certification?

25 responses

11 environments have an ISO27001 certification, for 8 this is in progress, while 6 of the TREs covered do not have this.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed security audits and certificates. One answer specified auditing against the Finnish secondary use act, designated here under ‘national’ measures, and one answer specified a Norwegian code of conduct for information security and data protection, likewise captured here under ‘national’ measures. Full answers can be found in the inventory.

National security audits were identified as the most common, with organisational audits also relatively common.

Are project areas fully isolated from each other?
24 responses

23 respondents reported that project areas are fully isolated from each other, while only one respondent marked this not to be the case.

How are project areas isolated from each other?

Firewalls	By use of network and storage virtualization
Network security policy	Access rights/control

VLAN separation	Secure project folders
Audit and logging	Data isolation through access control lists
Network segmentation	Zero-trust principles
User-level encryption	Storage segregation
Logical network isolation	

Table 2. Isolation methods overview (n = 11).

This was a free-text question, receiving 11 responses. This lower rate in answers is due to an amendment made to the survey after it had already opened, introducing this question after WP11 had an internal discussion that this key information should be captured. As such, early responses do not contain an answer to this question.

The table above lists measures taken to achieve project isolation. As this is sensitive information, detailed answers have been anonymised and can be found in full in Appendix 1, while the answers have been fully removed from the inventory. The answers suggest similar approaches in many instances, especially in network and storage isolation. Many respondents listed a cluster of the above isolation methods, signalling that TREs often use a set of isolation measures.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed security measures against unauthorised access. TRE-specific answers on security measures have been considered as sensitive data in the inventory and have thus been removed from it. The table above offers an anonymised summary.

Multi Factor Authentication (84%) and individual identification (76%) emerged as the most common security measures against unauthorised access. The process of individual identification will differ between service providers.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed security measures for mitigating data loss. TRE-specific answers on data loss measures have been considered as sensitive data in the inventory and have thus been removed from it. The table above offers an anonymised summary. One respondent clarified that “data backups are not complete but have to be agreed with each user/project separately.” This has been recorded under data backup as a measure used.

Data backup was the most common at 84%, with snapshots and cybersecurity measures present in around two thirds of the environments at 68% and 64% respectively.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed security measures for mitigating user misuse. TRE-specific answers on these measures have been considered as sensitive data in the inventory and have thus been removed from it. The table above offers an anonymised summary. One respondent noted that misuse is defined by the data controller, who may or may not then impose sanctions – this is recorded under ‘sanctions’ in the chart above.

All respondents mitigate misuse through authorised access, with user restrictions and user training also being common measures. Respondents also listed many other measures, including recordings, NDAs, policies, and user agreements.

5. Computing/analytics services provided

5.1 Computing and Analysis Services

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed operating systems. These responses can be found in full in the inventory. Linux emerged as the most common standard base operating system, with Windows coming third.

The Linux-based operating systems can be broken down as follows:

Within the Linux landscape, Ubuntu is by far the most common standard base operating system used, but Redhat and Rocky are also common.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed operating systems available for users. These responses can be found in full in the inventory.

Linux is the most common operating system available to users, with Windows as the second most common.

Is there access to HPC in/through the environment?
23 responses

Around 61% of environments have access to HPC.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed tooling. TRE-specific answers on tooling have been considered as sensitive data and have thus been removed from the inventory. The table above offers an anonymised summary.

There is variation between answers, but custom-made analysis software, Jupyter notebooks, and RStudio emerge as frequently used. Many of the replies emphasise that there are several tooling options available. One respondent describes their environment as tool-independent, as long as applications can be containerized in Docker; another noted that “available tooling and software depends on the SOPs defined between the PI and the hosting cloud site.”

Is there support for AI/machine learning?

23 responses

Nearly 74% of environments support AI/machine learning. The survey did not ask for details on how this is done, but the next iteration of the survey can take this into consideration as an area to build knowledge on.

5.2 User Rights

Are users allowed to import code/software/libraries?

24 responses

Nearly 88% of environments allow users to import code/software/libraries.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed import sources. These responses can be found in full in the inventory. “Network access regulated by TRE” was the most common import source, while many environments also reported individual import sources.

What is the user import size?

22 responses

Around a quarter of environments have limited user import sizes.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed user import types. 63% of the responses reported that any import type is possible, with source code, data, containers and text-only as common import types. One respondent specified that access and import is defined in the SOPs between the PI and the hosting cloud site.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed import connections. TRE-specific answers on import connection have been considered as sensitive

data and have thus been removed from the inventory. The table above offers an anonymised summary. An encrypted connection was the most frequently reported.

What conditions are there on users importing code/software/libraries?

23 responses

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed import conditions. TRE-specific answers on import conditions have been considered as sensitive data and have thus been removed from the inventory. The table above offers an anonymised summary. Manual checks for imports received almost 40% of answers, and automated checks 22%. 30% of environments did not have import restrictions.

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed measures. TRE-specific answers on measures against malicious code execution have been considered as sensitive data and have thus been removed from the inventory. The table above offers an anonymised summary. The most common measures are monitoring (64%) and root access restrictions (59%). Antivirus checks are also often done on imports (40%). The survey contained a typo on root access (spelled route), which may have impacted responses, but respondents likely recognised this error, and the data here is considered to have correctly identified root access as a measure against malicious code execution.

5.3 Data Discovery

Is there a public discovery service for datasets available in this TRE?

25 responses

Nearly two thirds of environments have a public discovery service for datasets. Links to these can be found in the inventory.

5.4 Federated Queries

This was a free-text question, and the full answers can be found in the inventory. Half of the environments did not support federated queries, for two the information was not available, and the remainder, around 36%, did support them. One respondent specified that “the service is built to support federated and linkable data. Data storage is federated, linkage/analysis is centralised.” Another stated that the environment “supports federated

queries for distributed analytics/federated learning. The central service distributes federated queries and aggregates results to provide only a final result to the user.”

This was a free-text question, and the full answers can be found in the inventory. Here, half of the environments did not support federated queries of metadata/data from external authorised users, a third did, and for the remainder the information was not available.

6. Reference Architecture

Institutional reference architecture	5
SATRE	4
Co-developing the Norwegian SPE requirements with the Norwegian health authorities	1
Custom built	1
Institutional in accordance with other European HPC systems (PRACE, EuroHPC, etc)	1
National reference architecture	1
Personal Health Train architecture	1
Proprietary, open-source	1
https://www.microdata.no/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Key-Architecture-Choices-in-Microdata.pdf	1
We fulfill most of the mandatory SATRE requirements	1

Alignment with EOSC ENTRUST blueprint and institutional reference architecture for de.NBI Cloud	1
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Table 3. Reference architecture responses (n = 18).

This was a multi-choice question, with “other” as an option to add any non-listed reference architectures. These responses can be found in full in the inventory as some have been abbreviated here. There was variation on what reference architecture is used, but SATRE received 22% of responses, with institutional reference architecture being the most common at almost 28%.

7. Discussion and conclusions

The updated TRE provider capabilities summarised in this report indicate both common practices and trends, as well as reflecting variety in the TRE landscape that is significant for the ENTRUST project and its goals.

TREs/SPEs continue to have **terminological and functional diversity**, suggesting that there are differences in how these secure environments are conceptualised. In this discussion section, we will use ‘TRE’ for these environments as an umbrella term, but as seen in the survey data this is not necessarily how these environments self-label. TRE service providers likewise have differing GDPR roles (data processors and data controllers), and the even split between public benefit and non-public benefit environments also speaks to TREs operating within a broad range of structures.

International accessibility showcases a range of approaches, many of which are flexible. There is a trend towards global collaboration that is overall discernible, but we also see national-only registration and access, reflecting policy-imposed limitations. The survey data indicates that international access/registration is often project-specific, and the environment is set up according to project specifications. TRE service providers are able to meet a variety of demands, therefore, and the overall trend toward cross-border access is promising for the ENTRUST project. Nearly two thirds of TREs also reported using private/premise clouds – the survey conflated these two, and a distinction will be made going forward. This nevertheless suggests that service providers prefer dedicated infrastructure that offers extensive control and security for the TRE.

Many TREs accept unrestricted **data types**, showing flexibility in data handling. Accepted data types also reflect formats that are commonly used, such as spreadsheet files and source code. In the minority are TREs that restrict data types, with certain format specifications.

Security measures and auditing show a broad range of efforts. Many TREs have an ISO27001 certification, and many are working towards this, suggesting that meeting international standards is a key requirement for these environments. National level compliance is also visible in the security measures. Nearly all TREs reported project area isolation, showing that this is a key standard; details on how areas are isolated gives only

partial information due to the late addition of the question, but firewalls and network separation were highlighted.

For **computing and analysis services**, Linux-based systems were the most popular, but there is both flexibility and range in operating systems used. The majority of the environments support HPC and AI-learning, which sets these environments up for ongoing development in these areas. Many also reported a wide range of tooling efforts, suggesting that TREs are comprehensive in this area.

In terms of **user rights**, the environments reflect adaptability for imports and most reported unrestricted import sizes and show flexibility also for import types. The presence of manual and automated checks, alongside monitoring and antivirus measures, indicates a layered security strategy to mitigate risks associated with imports. Import connections were most commonly encrypted or limited, hinting at institutional and national policies.

The vast majority of TREs supported public **dataset discovery** services. There was limited support for **federated queries**, signalling that this remains a significant area of development. This poses a challenge for ENTRUST as a project that aims to boost and support federation – based on the current capabilities, many TREs are not federation ready. Federated queries are, however, only one way to measure federation, and more focus should be placed in the project on determining federation readiness and by what metrics this can be determined. These federation related challenges will impact the work done by the ENTRUST project in the second half of its project timeline, as ENTRUST will have to mitigate the current landscape against project goals.

Finally, there was a wide range for **reference architectures** used – SATRE and institutional architectures were both common, but overall the TRE landscape remains mixed in this area, posing challenges for interoperability. This can, however, be an opportunity for the ENTRUST blueprint: in a mixed landscape such as this, a robust reference architecture has the opportunity to gain traction, especially if it reflects best practices and high standards at an international level.

Appendix 1: Anonymised free-text answer

How are project areas isolated from each other?
Access rights on the storage, logical network isolation.
By use of network, compute and storage virtualization.
Different networks
Each project is allocated a project folder within the TRE. It is a secure working area that can only be accessed by the approved researchers named on the project, plus the minimum number of required database infrastructure staff.
Every end-user operates in a designated area controlled by the service, and only indirectly accessible via metadata and the built-in analysis tool.
Firewalls
HPC nodes are dedicated to the project, with data isolation enforced through access control lists (ACLs)
Network Segmentation
<p>Project areas are isolated using a layered security model that incorporates zero-trust principles, alongside logical access controls, resource scoping, user-level encryption, and network virtualization and segmentation, are all implemented. Each project represents a distinct security and operational boundary, with isolation ensured through the following mechanisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Zero-trust principles: A zero-trust approach is applied where no user, device, or service is inherently trusted — even inside the platform perimeter. All access requests are explicitly authenticated, authorized, and continuously verified based on project membership, role, and context. There is no implicit trust between users, projects, or services. * Access control: Only users who have been explicitly granted membership in a project can access its data, applications, and computing resources. Fine-grained role-based access control (RBAC) ensures least-privilege permissions within each project.

* Storage segregation: Each project has an isolated storage namespace with strict enforcement of project-level access policies and quotas. There is no cross-project visibility or data leakage by design.

* User-level encryption: Users can encrypt files locally before uploading them. Encrypted data remains opaque to other users, including administrators, unless decrypted by the data owner. This ensures that sensitive information is protected even within shared project spaces.

* Compute isolation: Jobs and virtual environments execute in secure containers or VMs that are isolated per project and user. There is no runtime sharing of resources between projects.

* Network virtualization and segmentation: Each project operates within its own logically segmented virtual network. Internal communication is restricted to project members and their services. Software-defined networking (SDN) ensures that inter-project traffic is blocked unless explicitly permitted.

* Service separation: Applications are deployed in per-project sandboxes. Each instance has a unique service endpoint with access restricted to project members.

* Audit and logging: All user actions, data access events, and compute operations are logged separately per project. This supports full traceability, auditability, and compliance with data governance requirements.

Together, these mechanisms ensure strong isolation and security across project areas, making the service suitable for handling sensitive data in a multi-tenant national infrastructure.

Three-level separation: local firewall, network security policy, VLAN separation

Users have separate user workspaces, data are shared only with the user/owner and between the predefined group of users that are working on the same project. There are user access controls where each project can have its own users and permissions. We use separate storage folders / volumes. We use network segmentation but not really on the level of each project but more on the level of different departments (all network data is encrypted). For each project separated virtual machines/containers are used. Logs are user/project specific.

Appendix 2. Sensitive Information Removed or Anonymised from MS11

By Abdulrahman Azab, Sigma2

To preserve the security posture and integrity of participating Trusted Research Environments (TREs), the following categories of information have been excluded from the public version of the MS11 inventory or presented in anonymised/aggregated form in the summary:

1. Details of Project Isolation Mechanisms

- Examples of what has been removed/anonymized: Descriptions mentioning specific isolation strategies such as Kubernetes namespaces, OpenStack projects, VLAN IDs, firewall configurations, storage segregation mechanisms, and logical network segmentation per environment.
- Reason: These details can reveal the internal architecture and defensive layers of the TRE, which could aid malicious actors in crafting targeted attacks or identifying potential weaknesses.

2. Access and Authentication Configurations

- Examples: Specific implementation of MFA (e.g., hardware tokens vs. software apps), types of SSO solutions used, or project-specific authentication workflows.
- Reason: Detailed authentication mechanisms can expose attack surfaces or support adversaries in bypassing identity controls, particularly in environments where threat modeling depends on obscurity of implementation.

3. Import/Export Security Handling

- Examples: Environments that disclosed import/export validation methods, types of automated/manual checks, encrypted connection types, or virus scanning configurations.
- Reason: The specifics of how external data is verified or sanitized may reveal gaps or assumptions in threat detection, enabling data injection or evasion strategies.

4. Exact Tooling and Platform Descriptions

- Examples: Named platforms (e.g., UCloud, SATRE), container technologies used (Docker, Kubernetes), analysis environments, or unique endpoint implementations.
- Reason: Public disclosure of tooling ecosystems may enable supply-chain targeting or container escape attempts when attackers are familiar with the technology stack.

5. Network Topology and Architecture References

- Examples: Use of SDN, OpenStack isolation, private IP schemes, detailed internal segmentation strategies, custom-built vs. reference architecture specifics.
- Reason: Detailed network information can compromise network hardening and zoning strategies, providing attackers with information to bypass inter-zone protections or pivot within environments.

6. Audit Logging and Monitoring Strategies

- Examples: Specifics on what is logged, separation of log data by project, or retention and review policies.
- Reason: Knowing the extent and limitations of monitoring can inform adversaries of how to operate under the radar, delaying detection of unauthorized activities.

Actions Taken for MS11

- Named technologies or methods replaced with generalized terms (e.g., “network segmentation techniques”).
- Aggregated statistics used (e.g., “X% use Kubernetes namespaces”) instead of listing per-organization strategies.
- Where detail is essential for technical reproducibility or assessment, the sensitive parts have been moved to internal annexes or restricted deliverables, accessible only to trusted parties (e.g., reviewers, Commission officers).
- Data detailing sensitive TRE capabilities outlined in this appendix have been removed in full from the published version of the inventory